

ISic3243

I.Sicily inscription 3243

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 276

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Λόλλις · Εὐτύχης

2. Σαβείνα · ἰδίᾳ ·

3. συνβίῳ · ζῶν ἐποίη

4. σε ·

5. μνήμης χάριν

6. ἔζησεν ἔτη λε

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

Lollis Eutyches living, built this for his own partner, Sabeina, for the sake of her memory. She lived for 35 years

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645541

PHI 316228

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2004.0649

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 54.0905

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 105

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